

1 **Open Access and Altmetrics in the pandemic age:**
2 **Forescast analysis on COVID-19 literature**

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8 **Abstract** We present an analysis on the uptake of open access on COVID-
9 19 related literature as well as the social media attention they gather when
10 compared with non OA papers. We use a dataset of publications curated by
11 Dimensions and analyze articles and preprints. Our sample includes 11,686
12 publications of which 67.5% are openly accessible. OA publications tend to re-
13 ceive the largest share of social media attention as measured by the Altmetric
14 Attention Score. 37.6% of OA publications are bronze, which means toll jour-
15 nals are providing free access. MedRxiv contributes to 36.3% of documents in
16 repositories but papers in BiorXiv exhibit on average higher AAS. We predict
17 the growth of COVID-19 literature in the following 30 days estimating ARIMA
18 models for the overall publications set, OA vs. non OA and by location of the
19 document (repository vs. journal). We estimate that COVID-19 publications
20 will double in the next 20 days, but non OA publications will grow at a higher
21 rate than OA publications. We conclude by discussing the implications of such
22 findings on the dissemination and communication of research findings to mit-
23 igate the coronavirus outbreak.

24 **Keywords** altmetrics · scientometrics · coronavirus · COVID-19 · open
25 access · repositories · science of science · open science

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1 Introduction

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the COVID-19 a world pandemic (Organization et al., 2020). Since then, the spread of the disease has expanded, forcing governments to confine their population and enforce social distancing to reduce the spread of the virus. The gravity of the situation has led to an unprecedented scientific race to mitigate the effects of the pandemic (Torres-Salinas et al., 2020) which has overflowed the scientific scholarly communication system (Larrivière et al., 2020). The normal pace of scholarly communication has proven to be too slow and inefficient, leading to a complete transformation in the way new findings are reported and consumed. Traditional bibliometric databases such as Web of Science or Scopus, which index mainly published journal literature, have become almost instantly obsolete while journals are accelerating to an unprecedented rate their publication track for any COVID-related study. This has led scientists' attention to unexpected sources such as *ad hoc* compilations of scientific literature openly accessible and curated by the scientific community. Examples of such compilations are the CORD-19 dataset¹, a global community effort, the COVID-19 Database maintained by the WHO², or some publisher curated lists. These topic-specific databases are characterized by their daily update as well as including both, peer-reviewed and non-peer reviewed literature literature.

The COVID-19 pandemic has confronted scientists to an unprecedented challenge in which time and efficiency are critical. The exponential growth of scientific literature on the coronavirus outbreak and the means by which new findings are disseminated, disregarding the traditional status of journals for the sake of speed and efficiency (Larrivière et al., 2020), confront scientists to additional obstacles. They need to keep up with new scientific literature, be more critical than ever with non-peer-reviewed literature and respond to the the expectations of society. As a consequence, scientific discussions and conflicts are more public than ever (Gulbrandsen et al., 2020), revealing an additional threat, as socially responsible attitudes are crucial to stop the spread of the outbreak (Thelwall and Thelwall, 2020). Examples such as a recent paper suggesting the virus was man-made (Delgado López-Cózar et al., 2020) reveal that responsible communication to non-scientific audiences is essential to balance between open scientific debates and public outreach. In this new context, altmetrics gain more importance than ever, as they become the quickest vehicle to monitor social perception of science in an area where citations play a secondary role as they lack on speed to keep up the production and reception of new findings.

In this study we compare the growth on publications, citations and altmetric mentions to COVID-19 literature using the Dimensions dataset which includes publications, datasets, grants and clinical trials (Resources, 2020).

¹ <https://pages.semanticscholar.org/coronavirus-research>

² <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/global-research-on-novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov>

The general goal is to analyze the size of scientific literature is expected in relation to this crisis, as well as the size of the discussions as any type of analysis or tool built based on this increasing body of information will have to consider such growth rate. More specifically, in this study we aim at responding at the following research questions:

1. What are the differences in terms of access to COVID-19 related literature? We establish comparisons between OA and non-OA output as well as between journal articles and preprints to study the effectiveness of the communication strategies followed by scientists working on this subject.
2. What is the expected growth of both, scientific literature, citations and social media attention? By modelling our data we establish predictions to up to 30 days which will can help on the design of infrastructure and tools which will make use of this data.

2 Data and methods

2.1 Data collection

We use the Dimensions dataset on COVID-19 literature version 14, which was updated for the last time in April 14, 2020 (Resources, 2020). This dataset contains information on four document types: publications, datasets, clinical trials and grants. In this study we work with the publications dataset, which includes a total of 11,686 records. This dataset is much more restrictive than COVID-19, which employs a much wider criteria of inclusion (Colavizza et al., 2020). This set is retrieved from the Dimensions database after using the following search query³:

Year: 2020; Data Search: "2019-nCoV" or "COVID-19" or "SARS-CoV-2" or ("coronavirus" or "corona virus") and (Wuhan or China)

For each record it includes publication metadata as well as information on number of citations, Altmetric Attention Score, journal or repository and open access (OA) status. Table 1 offers a brief overview of the contents of the publication dataset with regard to publication type, document type and type of access. Dimensions provided OA information retrieved from Unpaywall, but assigns documents to one OA type exclusively, overriding cases in which there might be evidence of more than one OA type for a single document (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020).

In this study we restrict our analysis to two document types, that is, articles and preprints. The Dimensions dataset includes other document types such as monographs, book chapters and proceedings, but these only amount to a total of 278 records. We must also note that preprints and articles are document types unrelated to their OA status of the manuscript, as preprints (e.g., online first) can also be found in journals. After some normalization on the original dataset, we identified 67.5% of all COVID-19 related publications

³ Additional information on this dataset is available at <https://covid-19.dimensions.ai/>.

Table 1 Overview of the Dimensions dataset for COVID-19 related publications

Type of access	Journal	Repository	% preprints
Closed	3514	288	0.00
Bronze	3072	318	0.00
Green, Accepted	4	0	0.00
Green, Published	15	627	0.98
Green, Submitted	21	1538	0.99
Hybrid	458	626	0.00
Pure Gold	1205	0	0.00
Total	8289	3397	0.23

109 openly accessible, with 8.2% of closed publications deposited under embargo
 110 in repositories.

111 2.2 Methods

112 The focus of the paper is on the growth of publications as well as of social
 113 media attention. As a proxy for the latter we use the Altmetric Attention
 114 Score (AAS) provided in the original dataset. Altmetric scores can only be
 115 obtained for documents which include an identifier such as a DOI or a PMID.
 116 11,189 records in the Dimensions dataset include an identifier, that is 95.7%
 117 of the records. The AAS has been strongly criticized by the scientometric
 118 community (Gumpenberger et al., 2016; Mukherjee et al., 2018) as it is a
 119 composite measure difficult to interpret. In the case of altmetrics this becomes
 120 even more problematic as Altmetric.com (the altmetric platform behind the
 121 score) includes a plethora of diverse sources with little relation with each
 122 other. While these limitations are acknowledged, we used this indicator as
 123 an exploratory attempt to identify those documents with higher social media
 124 attention. In further analyses we plan to obtain additional information from
 125 Altmetric.com on the specific scores obtained by each paper in each of the
 126 platforms this database covers.

127 To establish prediction on publications, citations and altmetrics growth
 128 (with particular interest on OA) we address the problem as a one of time
 129 series prediction. To do so, we need adequate tools to analyze historical data
 130 and thus, making predictions Hassan (2014); de Oliveira and Oliveira (2018).
 131 There are several types of models that can be used for time-series forecasting
 132 Siami-Namini et al. (2018). In this study we make use of ARIMA (AutoRe-
 133 gressive Integrated Moving Average) Ho and Xie (1998), which is one of the
 134 most widely known approaches Hyndman and Athanasopoulos (2018). In this
 135 kind of models, the forecasts correspond to a linear combination of past values
 136 of the variable Hyndman and Khandakar (2008), explaining a given time series
 137 based on past values.

138 An ARIMA model is characterized by three parameters (p, d, q) where,

139 – p refers to the use of past values in the regression equation for the series

Fig. 1 Time trend on the accumulated number of records overall, in journals and in repositories

- 140 – d indicates the order of difference for attaining stationarity
- 141 – q determines the number of terms to include in the model

142 Here we obtain ARIMA models for the total number of publications, by
 143 location of the record (journal or repository) and OA status. All the analyses
 144 are conducted on an Ubuntu 18.04.1 machine with R version 3.6.3 and RStudio
 145 version 1.1.456. Figure 1 shows the publication time trends observed in the
 146 Dimensions dataset. As reported in a previous paper (Torres-Salinas, 2020)
 147 the literature on COVID-19 is growing at an exponential rate. If we consider
 148 the total number of publications, the value of R^2 is equal to 0.93. In the case
 149 of journal publications the value of R^2 is 0.92. In the case of repositories, we
 150 observe a much slower growth ($R^2 = 0.36$). Predictive models were obtained
 151 for each of the variables observed and subsequently estimated. These models
 152 will be referred to from here on as ARIMA(1,2,2) for the "Total" series,
 153 ARIMA(0,2,1) for the "Journal" series, and ARIMA(2,2,4) for the "repositories"
 154 series. Our 30 days predictions are based on these models.

155 3 Results

156 3.1 Descriptive analysis

157 Table 2 provides an overview of the dataset used. A total of 11,686 papers
 158 were retrieved, out of which 7,884 (68%) are available in OA. This proportion
 159 decreases during the month of April. Despite the fact that this analysis covers
 160 three and 1/2 months, a total of 27,129 citations have already been made.
 161 This means on average 2.32 citations per paper. This average is even higher
 162 for non OA publications, which receive an average number of citations of 3.28.

163 These papers have raised an unprecedented amount of social media atten-
 164 tion according to their AAS. On average, these documents receive an AAS of

a. Number of papers in <i>Dimensions</i>			
	Totals	Open Access	Non Open Access
▪ January	313	261	52
▪ February	1039	847	192
▪ March	4815	3980	835
▪ April (until 04/13)	5519	2796	2723
	11686	7884 (68%)	3802 (32%)
b. <i>Attention Altmetric Score & citations</i>			
	Accumulated	Average per paper	Max Value
<i>Altmetric Attention Score- AAS</i>	1373008	117.49	27609
▪ Open Access	1200466	152.25	27609
▪ Non Open Access	172542	45.38	7680
<i>Citations</i>	27129	2.32	1238
▪ Open Access	25914	0.31	1238
▪ Non Open Access	1215	3.28	127
c. Journals, repositories and main information sources			
	Nr Papers	AAS accumulated	Citations accumulated
Journals	8288	1105043	24604
Repositories	3397	267964	2525
▪ <i>Information sources:</i>			
▪ Pubmed*	5143	998682	24008
▪ PMC*	2330	424181	13973
▪ BioRxiv	346	77411	1029
▪ MedRxiv	1232	154540	1260

Table 2 Description of the dataset by type of access. **A** Time trend, **B** Altmetric Attention Score and citation indicators, and **C** distribution of records, Altmetric Attention Score and citations by location (journals or repositories).

* These two repositories include also journal literature and hence overlap with the two location types.

165 117, which is even higher in the case of OA papers (152.25). In this sense, we
 166 observe differences depending on the location of the record. Journal articles
 167 receive higher citations than those stored in repositories, but there are differ-
 168 ences by repository. PubMed and PMC receive a considerably higher number
 169 of social media attention than the rest of the repositories. Although BioRxiv
 170 and MedRxiv provide a lower number of documents to the dataset, they still
 171 attract a high number of citations (in the case of the former) and social media
 172 attention (for the latter).

173 3.2 Open Access and social media attention

174 Figure 2 shows the distribution of AAS (A) and numberthe relation between
 175 the number of documents and AAS each receives (B) by OA status. Most of

Fig. 2 Altmetric Attention Score: Open Access and Non Open Access

176 the papers on COVID-19 are OA and reach higher values of AAS than non-OA
 177 papers. For instance, two papers obtained AAS values of 27,609 (Nat Med 26,
 178 450-452, 2020) and 21,738 (N Engl J Med, 382, 1564-1567, 2020) respectively.
 179 Likewise 15 OA papers obtained a score of at least 10,000 AAS, accumulating
 180 a total of 215,885. These fifteen papers alone add up to more AAS than the
 181 entire set of papers published as non OA (Table 2).

182 Figure 3 shows the distribution of AAS (A) and the size of the output (B)
 183 by OA type. Bronze OA documents tend to receive a higher AAS and represent
 184 the largest share of COVID-19 related publications (3,072). Overall OA papers,
 185 either We observe that OA papers published in journals (regardless of the OA
 186 type: bronze, hybrid or pure), predominate. In relation to AAS, bronze papers
 187 have an average of 249 and papers with higher AAS are within this modality.
 188 Hybrid and gold OA papers receive less attention, 154 and 61 on average,
 189 respectively.

190 In Figure 4 we shift our focus to records deposited in repositories. The
 191 repository with the largest number of publications is PMC, with a total of 2,330
 192 papers and an average AAS of 182. Here we must note that PMC not only
 193 includes self-archived documents, but also indexes OA journals (Robinson-
 194 Garcia et al., 2020). The second largest repository is medRxiv with a total
 195 of 1,232 and an average AAS of 125 per document. Despite being the repository
 196 with the lowest number of records included (387), documents indexed in
 197 BioRxiv receive on average, the highest AAS (223). All documents in BioRxiv
 198 have receive at least an AAS of 1. The rest of the repositories analyzed (Chem-
 199 Rxiv, JMIR Preprints, Research Square and SSRN) have a peripheral role on
 200 production and visibility of COVID-19 related publications.

Fig. 3 Overview of social media attention on open access. **A** Altmetric Attention Score distribution by OA type and **B** Number of records and AAS received by paper by OA type

Fig. 4 Overview of social media attention for documents deposited in repositories. **A** Altmetric Attention Score distribution by repository and **B** Number of records and AAS received by paper by repository

201 3.3 Predictive analysis: ARIMA models

202 Figure 5 shows the accumulated time trend on number of publications and
 203 by journal and repository, as well as the predicted trends according to the
 204 obtained ARIMA model.

Fig. 5 Growth evolution and predicted trend on COVID-19 related literature and by location (journals and repositories)

205 Paying attention to Figure 5, it can be seen that the estimate made by the
 206 predictive models at 30 days is of a growing trend in the number of publica-
 207 tions. The ARIMA model forecast for total publications starts on 14/04/200
 208 with 12254 publications and ends on 13/05/2020 with 27162 publications. In
 209 the case of journals it starts with 8601 publications and ends with 17660. The
 210 repositories will grow at a slower rate, the forecast starts with 3538 publica-
 211 tions and ends with 7712. The data indicate that total publications will
 212 double in about 20 days, journal publications will double in about 24 days,
 213 and repository publications will double in about 24 days

214 Figure 6 shows the accumulated time trend as well as the predicted trend
 215 differentiating between OA and non OA publications. The ARIMA model fore-
 216 cast for OA papers starts on April 14, 2020 with 8,067 publications and ends
 217 on May 13, 2020 with 13,359 publications. According to these predictions, non
 218 OA publications will grow at faster rate than OA publications. The forecast
 219 starts with 4,075 publications and ends with 11,992. It can be said that OA
 220 publications will double every 30 days and non OA publications will double
 221 every 14 days. The differences between the number of OA and non OA pub-
 222 lications appears to be narrowing as the prediction progresses. By the end of
 223 the forecast, the central role of open access will not be as clear as it was in
 224 early February and March.

225 4 Discussion and further research

226 This paper reports on the growth of scientific literature, citations and social
 227 media attention revolving around COVID-19 literature. For this, it uses the

Fig. 6 Growth evolution and predicted trend on COVID-19 related literature by OA and non OA.

228 Dimensions dataset (Resources, 2020) which is openly accessible and has been
 229 updated daily until its last update on April 14, 2020. While the dataset itself
 230 is not free of limitations, and other COVID-19 datasets are being used alter-
 231 natively, it is the one coming from the largest scientific database as compared
 232 with Web of Science and Scopus (Torres-Salinas et al., 2020). Furthermore,
 233 the search query used seems to be much more restrictive than other used else-
 234 where, which can introduce some noise when identifying the scientific corpus
 235 specifically dealing with this virus (Colavizza et al., 2020).

236 The findings reported here shows that many journals (e.g., New England
 237 Journal of Medicine, The Lancet, JAMA, Nature) are doing an important
 238 effort to prioritize the urgency of the current situation over their monetary
 239 benefits by providing COVID-19 related literature in OA. This is an unprece-
 240 dented event which should not go unnoticed, and explains to a large extent the
 241 large shares of OA literature identified related with the coronavirus outbreak.
 242 The interest on scientific development on this front go beyond the scientific
 243 realm as the high social media attention revolving these documents shows.
 244 Scientific advancements are reported daily in the news media, discussed on
 245 Twitter and used for decision-making by politicians. Indeed, scientific efforts
 246 have not only focused on mitigating the pandemic, but have also responded
 247 to social concerns, such as those derived from the rise of fake news (Andersen
 248 et al., 2020).

249 The amount of literature produced since the coronavirus outbreak suggests
 250 an exponential growth on the number of publications produced, citations and
 251 social media mentions. If we want to be able to keep up with such growth
 252 and produce tools and analyses on such increasing corpus, some preparation
 253 is needed. Our estimates indicate that this number of records will duplicate

every 14 days if the current rhythm of production continues. First reactions praised OA efforts from the scientific community and how these confronted the "normal" speed of science (Larrivière et al., 2020). However, our analysis shows a great dependency on journal literature and specifically on the role of major toll journals which have made openly accessible COVID-19 related literature as an exceptional measure. This reflects a great dependency on the traditional journal publishing system. Furthermore, our predictions estimate a higher growth for non OA literature in the near future. This trend, if confirmed, can become a great obstacle on the advancement of a cure for COVID-19 as well as on mitigating collateral damages from the pandemic.

Social media attention revolves mainly around OA publications, but again, here the role of toll journals opening their contents through bronze OA is crucial, followed by hybrid OA and gold OA, again reflecting that, despite the urgency, the traditional and mechanisms of scholarly publishing are still in place, along with all their deficiencies (Gadd, 2020).

That said, any conclusions on the predictions reported must be taken with caution as we live in a constantly changing situation, closely linked to the mitigation of the pandemic and political actions derived from it. Still, analyses such as the present can help us contextualize the phenomenon and provide alternative views from which scientometricians can contribute.

5 Summary of key findings

In this section we provide a brief summary of the main findings reported in this study.

1. 11,686 publications on COVID-19 were retrieved. 68% are OA. 27,129 citations have already been made. This means on average 2.32 citations per publication
2. On average publications receive an Altmetric Attention Score of 117, which is even higher in the case of Open Access papers (152.25)
3. Most of the publications on COVID-19 are OA and receive higher social media attention than non OA papers.
4. Most of the OA publications are bronze OA. These are receiving the highest social media.
5. OA papers published in scientific journals predominate. This fact emphasizes the central role of journals and peer review versus early access to preprints.
6. Pubmed is the repository with the largest number of publications, followed by medRxiv. Documents indexed in BioRxiv receive on average, the highest social media attention.
7. We expect that the total number of COVID-19 related publications will double in 20 days. Journal articles will double in 24 days, while papers in repositories will grow at a slower rate.
8. We expect non OA papers to grow at a faster rate than OA publications. By mid-May the number of non OA papers will have almost tripled.

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